

Representations of and by the Extended Mind

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> Abstract • The role of representation in the extended mind is central to understanding the philosophical commitments of the hypothesis and its relation to other accounts of cognition. While the target article provides an important analysis of the development and outlook for the extended mind and its relation to enactivism and active inference, it does not discuss the possibility of the free-energy framework as non-representational. I argue that such a reading allows for more fruitful exchanges between the extended mind, enactivism, and active inference.

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« 1 » Both philosophy of mind and philosophy of science have dealt intensively with the problem of representation in two mutually entangled questions:

- Do our models represent mind-independent properties of the world (Bailer-Jones 2006)?
- Does the mind represent properties of the world internally (Kirchhoff 2018)?

« 2 » In his target article, Timotej Prosen extends the extended-mind hypothesis of Andy Clark and David Chalmers (1998) with a non-representationalist twist. Discussing the often-cited example of Otto's notebook that is used in a navigation task, Clark and Chalmers seem to consider the written information in the notebook as representing something external. However, Evan Thompson and Mog Stapleton (2008) raise the point that enactive cognition does away with the distinction between internal and external representation, and also Prosen goes further than Clark and Chalmers in discussing what role representations in cognitive processes of an extended mind could play. His "moving boundary, plastic core" analogy is an elegant addition to the original extended-mind account, but it leaves open some of the functional aspects of representation.

« 3 » Prosen (§38) discusses the philosophical implications of a representationalist interpretation in relation to active inference and enactivism and pits one against the other. It is unfortunate, though, that he does not consider recent discussions on the philosophical foundations of the free-energy framework and active inference. Thomas van Es and Inês Hipólito (2020) argue that an instrumentalist reading that regards the notion of a model as a useful tool rather than effectively implemented in cognitive systems, is both philosophically coherent and still explanatorily relevant. While realist interpretations of active inference necessitate a representationalist model of the environment, recent developments of the free-energy principle and related theories, such as the Bayesian brain approach and predictive processing, point in a different direction (Ramstead et al. 2020). Reductionist readings attempt to find a biophysical principle for life and mind, but more recent research has been exploring the connection with embodiment and enactive cognition. An important insight marks the idea that to be consistent with the scientific approaches incorporating enactivism, we also have to switch our perspective on what scientific models represent. Even a computational model such as the Markov-blanket formalism, which is at the heart of active inference and free energy, needs to be re-evaluated from a modelling perspective. If we analyse how models of the mind are used in scientific practice, the simple picture of direct representation begins to crumble.

« 4 » Paul Humphreys (2002) provides a thorough analysis of computational models in science and how they are applied and interpreted in interdisciplinary research. His notion of a "computational template" provides a useful tool to understand that the active-inference framework comes with different ontological commitments depending on the problem we try to solve. A computational template consists of shared equations applied in different scientific fields and to a diverse range of phenomena. For example, the free-energy framework can be understood as such a computational tool applicable in physics, chemistry, computer science, and cognition. Humphreys emphasizes that with computational templates, the same mathematical skeleton is filled with

different interpretations when we tackle different phenomena with the same computational model. In the case of free energy, we end up with a diverse range of applications to organisms, neural networks, or human decision-making. From the perspective of philosophy of science, Mel Andrews (2021) argues that what seems to be a reduction of all these phenomena to one set of equations turns out to be a plethora of different models. While I agree with the assumption that representationalist active inference and a non-representationalist version of the extended mind are not compatible, there are also non-representationalist interpretations of predictive processing and the active-inference framework (Kirchhoff 2018). So, the article makes me wonder: **Is the third wave of extended mind still incompatible with active inference if we interpret the framework without strict representationalism? [Q1](#)**

« 5 » When discussing the representational question of cognition, what is missing is a process-oriented perspective that is about the act of representing itself. The artefactual account of scientific modelling regards the model-building process as an active part of sense-making (Knuuttila 2011). It highlights the role of modelling in epistemology that goes beyond the goal of accurately representing a mind-independent reality. Rather, we *make sense* with and through models, scientific or otherwise. Models are artefacts that are part of our cognitive processes. With regard to the plasticity of the boundary between cognitive agent and environment, this perspective goes hand in hand with the third wave of extended-mind research: We use tools to interact with and make sense of the environment, since they are an essential part of our cognitive process. So, the question of whether tools are part of the core or the boundary is essential to both the extended-mind and the scientific-modelling discussion. What are the epistemic tools, or artefacts, used in active inference? The whole framework builds on the measure of free energy, a quantity that has not been directly measured in the brain, but acts as a measure of complexity of a cognitive model (Friston 2009). The main idea is that minimizing free energy corresponds to maximizing predictive power with the simplest model possible. Interpreting models as part of the cognitive agent leads to a representationalist perspec-

tive. However, taking a step back and seeing models as artefacts in our sense-making of cognitive agents provides a more grounded perspective: we reduce our uncertainty about the cognitive agent by modelling it as a free-energy agent. This self-consistent perspective can be found in radical predictive processing (Clark 2015) and the idea of enactive inference (Ramstead 2021). Accepting this perspective means seeing representations as quick and imperfect tools to enact a lifeworld rather than as rich internal structures that make further interaction with the environment obsolete. We can predict the delicious taste of a chocolate cookie independently of whether we have a very detailed representation of it.

« 6 » If scientific modelling is nothing more than cognitive modelling, we have to take into consideration the limited information we have about ourselves and our environment. This limitation also applies to the scientific modelling of mental processes. Given the usefulness of computational models in neuroscience, the argument that our models about cognition have to be a direct representation of the cognitive processes themselves can be misleading. A position that has been defended by David Kirsh (1991) before enactivism and the extended mind hypothesis. Just because there is an efficient way to describe neuroimaging data by using a set of equations does not mean that the set of equations has any ontological status. We actively represent certain parts of the neuronal system by fitting them into the narrow frame of thinking described by our models. In the modelling process, we naturally omit details, idealize complex relations, and make abstractions to arrive at an applicable epistemological tool. However, the lack of detail in our models is not due to shortcomings of the modelling process in particular. It is part of the scientific approach to create useful maps, while, by contrast, representing the whole territory in all its details, even in theory, would make the map useless, as it would be as complex as the territory itself. Hipólito (2022) argued that the search for neural representation of our models in the brain comes from the underlying assumption that all cognition is based on computation – an assumption that goes against both enactivism and the dynamic-systems approach because it ignores the environment, the body

and all complex interactions between mind, body, and environment. Taking a step back is necessary to understand the mathematical tools of computational neuroscience as artefacts of sense-making rather than as accurate descriptions of the mind. Let me emphasize that this does not imply anti-realism about models, but highlights the interactive nature of scientific tools linking agents and their environment.

« 7 » To summarize, I would like to emphasize the two dimensions of representation in neuroscience. One deals with the methodological approach of the researchers themselves, while the other covers how we understand representation in cognitive models. Prosen's article compares enactivism and active inference in relation to novel developments in extended-mind research. In contrast to Prosen, I argue that after re-evaluating our understanding of representation, it turns out that these approaches are complementing rather than opposing each other. Cognitive representations do not have to directly correspond to objects in a mind-independent world to be useful both scientifically and cognitively. Indirect representations and the process of representing can be used to describe cognitive dynamics without making transcendental claims about their being images of mind-independent properties. Tarja Knuuttila's artefactual account and Humphreys's notion of computational templates provide arguments for the usefulness of models beyond direct representation. The former deals directly with sense-making through models and the latter shows how models are interpreted beyond their mathematical structure. They both point out that concepts are added to equations when applied to specific phenomena, since every novel application entails new interpretations. The argument in Prosen's target article could be complemented by recent formulations of active inference that take a non-representationalist perspective. These developments dissolve the opposition between active inference and enactivism, and taking this perspective shows that both are in line with sense-making as an active and relational process. The co-construction of agent and environment is a crucial point for all contemporary theories of the mind and future developments need to incorporate these processes.

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Extended Plastic Inevitable

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> Abstract • We argue that the free-energy principle (FEP) can indeed be used to articulate a conception of the boundaries of cognitive systems that meets the desiderata of third-wave extended-mind research. We point out that Markov blankets under the FEP definitionally constitute the means through which internal and external states are coupled, and so do not isolate systems from their environment. We argue that the nested, multiscale boundaries of the FEP formulation are indeed plastic and open to re-negotiation. Finally, we appeal to the formulation of niche construction under the FEP to argue that the extension of cognitive boundaries in this formulation is both synchronous and diachronic.

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Introduction

« 1 » Timotej Prosen's target article "A Moving Boundary, a Plastic Core" contributes compellingly to discussions of the con-

ception of the boundaries of cognitive systems that ought to figure in the third wave of extended-mind research (Kirchhoff 2012; Kirchhoff & Kiverstein 2019). More specifically, Prosen proposes that one can leverage notions from the enactive approach to cognitive science (Di Paolo 2009; Di Paolo & De Jaegher 2017), and from predictive processing (Hohwy 2014; Clark 2015) and the free-energy principle (FEP) (Friston 2020; Ramstead, Kirchhoff et al. 2021) in computational neurobiology, to formulate a unified conception of the boundaries – and the identity – of extended cognitive systems that is suitable for novel work in third-wave extended-mind research.

« 2 » The third wave of the extended mind features a specific conception of cognitive systems and their boundaries that emphasizes their plasticity and the extension of their dynamics over time. Namely, proponents of the third wave of the extended mind argue that the boundaries of cognitive systems are open to negotiation or moving, and that they can change over time to integrate components that were once external to the system; and they claim that the identities of cognitive systems are also plastic, subject to flux over time. To say that a boundary is moving means that it is shaped dynamically, in a temporally extended process, and that it is not static but rather that it can reform and re-assemble over time. That systems have a plastic core identity entails that what it means for a cognitive system to be "the kind of system that it is" is itself a moving target; the identity of a cognitive system – and what counts as meaningful for the system – are open to change, such that agents are continually modified by the new components that they integrate dynamically into their boundaries. Thus, on the third-wave conception, the extended cognitive system is not fixed once and for all, but rather evinces metastable boundaries; and the cognitive system itself is not centred on the organism, but rather, constitutively includes elements that lie outside its body.

« 3 » The target article presents the argument according to which core constructs from the enactive approach, predictive processing, and the FEP can be used to articulate a conception of the boundaries of cognitive systems that is suitable for third-wave extended-mind research. It argues that

one can draw on the notions of operational closure and autonomy from the enactive literature to account for moving boundaries in a manner suitable to third-wave extended-mind research. It is further suggested that the FEP can provide us with a complementary notion of a plastic core that is apt to account for the plasticity of system identity. In addition, crucially, the author claims that the conception of boundaries that follows from predictive processing and the free-energy principle – and that is operationalized by Markov blankets – is too rigid to do work in third-wave extended mind. This is because FEP-theoretic boundaries (allegedly) causally isolate the cognitive system from its environment in a way that precludes genuine cognitive extension and plasticity. Indeed, Prosen prefers to leverage the kind of dynamical self-assembly that is foregrounded in enactive accounts of the boundaries of cognitive systems.

« 4 » We broadly endorse the spirit of the arguments on offer but wish to make three remarks on this discussion. We claim –

- that the Markov blankets of the FEP formulation do not isolate a system from its environment, rather they are the means by which a particular system and its environment are coupled at all;
- that the notion of boundary in FEP is formulated in a multi-scale manner that already evinces the kind of plasticity that the author desires for third-wave extended-mind research; and
- that FEP adds a critical dimension to the idea of extending the boundaries of cognitive systems by appealing to constructs from niche-construction theory.

These claims suggest that Markov blankets may offer useful tools for translating narrative treatments of extended mind into formal accounts that can be used to simulate, predict, and quantify third-wave notions, via mathematical or numerical analysis.

Markov blankets are the means by which internal and external states are coupled

« 5 » A first, critical remark is in order, before getting into the specifics of system boundaries under the FEP. It should be highlighted that the FEP – and the Bayesian mechanics that attends its application (Sakthivadivel 2022) – is at its core a state-